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Pedagogical conditions of development of creative thinking in primary school children

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Abstract. Modernization of the education system in our country implies the development of new approaches to teaching, upbringing and development of students. New needs of society dictate the demand for a creatively active personality, capable of solving problems in non-standard conditions, flexibly and independently using acquired knowledge in various life situations. An active life position is manifested in the attitude of a person to the surrounding reality and is formed in the process of various types of activity, and, above all, learning. Primary school age is an important stage in the development of a child, since during this period there are great opportunities to influence his personal formation. Unfortunately, the existing system of school education actually does not contain special measures aimed at the consistent and systematic identification and development of creativity and productive imagination in schoolchildren. As a result, it is customary to evaluate not the act of creativity itself, but its final product.

Keywords: spectrum, tendency, ability, exteriorization, creativity, primary school age, creativity development, creative approach, stimulation of creativity.

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Introduction. Among the priority strategies for modernizing modern education remains the focus on developing the creative potential of schoolchildren as a determining condition for flexible adaptation to rapidly changing social realities. The relevance and significance of this task is reflected in scientific publications and can be substantiated by the facts of state support for multi-aspect research on the problems of creativity.

When considering the concept of «pedagogical conditions» in psychological and pedagogical scientific schools [1], several of its interpretations can be distinguished:

- «a result oriented towards the purposeful selection, design and application of content elements, methods (techniques), organizational forms of training aimed at achieving a result» (V.I. Andreev);

- «certain external circumstances that have a significant impact on the outcome and effectiveness of the educational process, consciously designed by the teacher, aimed at achieving a certain educational effect» (Borytko N.M.);
- «a substantive characteristic of certain components of the educational system oriented towards content, organizational forms, teaching aids and the nature of the relationship between the teacher and the child» (Zvereva M.V.);
- «the unity of objective resources of content, forms, methods, means and the spatial-material environment, which are aimed at solving educational problems» (Nain A.Ya.).

To summarize the above approaches, pedagogical conditions are understood as the unity of necessary and sufficient measures of influence (determining its content, forms and methods), ensuring the effectiveness of the educational process [13].

Materials and methods. Since 1975, the World Council for Gifted and Talented Children has been in existence, which coordinates work on the study, education and upbringing of extraordinary children, and organizes international scientific contacts. And although, as B.M. Teplov wrote, the height of giftedness is revealed only by the results of a person's life work, its direction and uniqueness are manifested much earlier: in stable interests and inclinations, in varying degrees of success in performing various types of activities, in the comparative ease of mastering various subjects. The study and analysis of philosophical, psychological, and pedagogical literature shows that the concept of «creativity» is quite extensive and attracts researchers from a large number of branches of scientific knowledge. Initially, the problem of the phenomenon of creativity was considered from the point of view of the traditions of mythology and religion. Creativity from the point of view of an integral property of God, creation from nothing; a certain mystification was put into this concept [1]. In the philosophical dictionary, the concept of «creativity» is presented as a purposeful human activity that carries a certain transformative force [3]. Studying creativity from the point of view of a philosophical category, it is necessary to turn to such a central property of human consciousness as intentionality. The etymology of the word «intentionality» means «intention». In philosophy, this category is a phenomenon that is aimed at a certain object, i.e. determines the vector of any activity. If we consider creativity from the standpoint of intentionality, then we can typologize creativity according to the principle of the direction of creative vectors as follows:

1. The interiorized type of creativity is a vector of creativity directed inside the subject of creativity (i.e. into subjective reality). The interiorized type of creativity is

the creation of one's self, one's personality. The essence of this type of creativity comes down to the accumulation of energy potential in the depths of the human soul.

2. The exteriorized type of creativity is a vector of creativity directed outside the subject of creativity (i.e. from the outside into objective reality itself). Exteriorization is the rarest creative phenomenon, since in order to create something outside oneself (i.e. in objective reality), it is necessary to have a certain energy reserve that would be sufficient for this type of activity [4].

N.A. Berdyaev interpreted the concept of «creativity» as freedom of the individual. In his works, he states: «Creativity purifies and elevates a person. Creativity is always a positive experience, the revelation of the self, a deep experience, overcoming oneself» [5]. In psychological studies of various methodological directions, the phenomenon of creativity is studied in the most detail, interpreted from various positions. Thus, Z. Freud, the founder of psychoanalytic theory, defined creativity as one of the forms of personality activity that can arise in the process of relieving internal stress by redirecting one's energy to achieve positive, socially approved goals. This phenomenon was called sublimation by Z. Freud [6]. Later, in humanistic psychology, in the works of A. Maslow, K. Rogers, a different direction in studying the phenomenon of creativity appears. Humanistic psychologists describe creativity from the point of view of the ability to deeply understand and realize one's own experience, as self-actualization and the ability to self-express [7].

Results. Consequently, already at primary school age, favorable prerequisites for the appropriation of creative patterns and the transformation of one's own experience of creative activity as an important source of personal growth and self-development are formed. At the same time, despite the long-term, stable interest in the designated problems, a number of scientific aspects in the problematic of creativity remain relevant due to the insufficiently studied, ambiguous or contradictory nature of the presented data. Among them are the category of «creativity» in the conceptual field of creativity, the context of «development of creativity» in general, as well as «development of creativity of primary school students in the pedagogical process», in particular [12].

The historical context of the phenomenon under study illustrates the peaks and troughs of research interest in the problems of creativity in the scientific community. The absence of a reliable stable connection between intelligence and creativity contributed to the development of approaches: personal motivational and psychometric. There is a tendency to isolate creativity research as an independent direction in the problematic area of creativity (creative thinking, etc.). The most controversial issues remain the identification and measurement of creativity. By now,

various approaches to the diagnosis of individual creative manifestations have developed, but among specialists, both in our country and abroad, there is no unanimity regarding the reliability, validity, and reliability of the diagnostic methods and techniques used [8].

Discussion. Creativity is the creative abilities of an individual that characterize the readiness to create and accept completely new ideas that differ significantly from traditional or generally accepted ones, included in the structure of giftedness as an independent factor. Creativity is also understood as the ability to solve problems that arise within the static system itself. Referring to the interpretation of Abraham Maslow, creativity is understood as the creative orientation of an individual, inherent in everyone, but which is lost by most people in the process of life in the process of influence of society, the system of upbringing and education. The need for the formation and development of creativity in primary school students is determined by the basic determinant of social creativity, attitudes towards the practical orientation of the individual, the manifestation of his creative individuality, based on the conceptual psychological principles of upbringing and training of a creative personality. The relevance of the study is due to the need to develop technological and scientific psychological and pedagogical support for the implementation and development of the creative potential of an individual; revealing existing contradictions and defining the social demand of society for a creative personality [11].

In psychological and pedagogical studies of creativity, the period of primary school age is of the greatest interest. A significant contribution to the development of the theory of creativity was made by scientists: Bogoyavlenskaya D.B., Venger L.A., Dyachenko O.M., Druzhinin V.N., Zaporozhets A.V., Leontyev A.N., Matyushkin A.M., Poddyakov N.N., Kudryavtsev V.A., Leites N.S., Heller K., Guilford J. [9] and many other domestic and foreign teachers and psychologists. In their works, creativity is studied as a special characteristic of mental activity, which differs from other mental processes that reveal the connection with the personal characteristics and imagination of a primary school student. In the practice of primary school, there is a tendency for primary school teachers to increase their attention to the development of creative abilities of a primary school child. One of the urgent tasks that methodologists, teachers and psychologists set for themselves is to improve the methods of personality-oriented interaction with primary school students, which contributes to the disclosure of the creative beginning of primary school students.

Every year, the process of development and testing of educational programs is significantly activated, in which the issues of creativity development in primary school age are seriously and thoroughly activated. However, testing of their content

component is not always successful, and the reason is the lack of diagnostic tools for identifying primary school students with an increased level of creative abilities. Based on the above, the issues of creativity development appear as significant and relevant in the personal development of a primary school student.

In the system of primary general education, the problem of creativity development based on the use of effective technologies is not given enough attention. The issue of designing pedagogical conditions for the development of creativity in primary school students is especially urgent.

Numerous studies in the field of creativity have revealed a certain set of traits that can be classified as creative. First of all, we can include self-confidence, independence of judgment, the ability to notice the attractiveness in difficulties, aesthetic orientation and the ability to take risks.

Creative product. As a rule, a person begins to create something new, original not for the sake of social recognition, but in order to experience that state of flight that gives him the opportunity to feel like a person.

One of the most important operations that can "work" during the creative process is the comparison operation: semantic connections are established between elements based on: random connection or semantic synthesis without determining reproduction and semantic connections. Thus, products (ideas, hypotheses, behavioral acts) can be considered original (creative), meaningless and stereotypical [10].

Conclusion. In primary school age, children who show a high level of creativity are often egocentric in their interpretation of phenomena and events. Egocentrism is a term given by Piaget, which helps to understand the qualitative differences between the animistic, intuitive perception of primary school children and the more rational, reality-oriented view of older primary school children. Sometimes children who show a high level of creativity suffer from some social rejection and non-recognition by their peers, and this develops a negative perception of themselves, as evidenced by many studies. In terms of developing a healthy self-perception and a sense of worth, the most useful thing is to communicate with similarly gifted children, and from a very early age. Families in which it is customary to help each other and where parents, sisters and brothers do everything together also reinforce the positive self-perception of each child. Thus, the features of creativity development in children of primary school age are:

1. Originality, non-triviality, unusualness of the expressed ideas, a pronounced desire for intellectual novelty.

2. Figurative adaptive flexibility, i.e. the ability to change the perception of an object in such a way as to see its new sides hidden from observation.

3. Semantic spontaneous flexibility, i.e. the ability to produce a variety of ideas in an uncertain situation.

4. Fluency characterizes the fluency of thinking and is determined by the total number of answers.

5. Flexibility is the ability to quickly switch and is determined by the number of classes (groups) of these answers.

6. Accuracy is the harmony, logicity of thinking, the choice of an adequate solution corresponding to the set goal.

References:

1. Бабич О.М., Вьюнова, Н.И., Гайдар, К.М. Развитие творческих способностей у младших школьников. - М., 2018. – 236 с.
2. Банзелюк Е.И. Возрастная динамика показателей креативности у младших школьников // Вопросы психологии. 2018. – 125 с.
3. Валуева Е. А. Характеристики задач в экспериментальных исследованиях творческого мышления: Психология – наука будущего. М., 2017. - С. 77–80.
4. Васильева Е. А. Теоретические аспекты развития творческого мышления в младшем школьном возрасте [Электронный журнал] / Е. А. Васильева // Молодой ученый. – 2015. – №11. – Режим доступа: <https://moluch.ru>, свободный, Яз. русс. 1717-1719 с.
5. Гасимова В. А. Креативность, обработка информации и внимание // Ананьевские чтения. СПб., 2017. - С. 6–8.
6. Давыдов В.В. Эльконин Д. Б. Вопросы психологии учебной деятельности младших школьников / В.В. Давыдов, Д.Б. Эльконин, Москва: Просвещение, 2018. – 196 с.
7. Ефимова О. И. Различия в образах воображения. М., 2017. Т. 1.- 350 с.
8. Ильин Е.П. Психология творчества, креативности, одаренности / раздел 1, гл.1 Е. П. Ильин. – Санкт-Петербург: Питер, 2011. – 23 с.
9. Концепции Ж.Пиаже, под ред. Реана А. А. 2002 Часть1, Глава 8 / «Психология человека от рождения до смерти» [Электронная библиотека] – Режим доступа: <http://pedlib.ru>, свободный, Яз. русс.
10. Корчаловско Н.В., Посевина Г.Д. Комплексные занятия по развитию творческих способностей дошкольников: Методическое пособие. Ростов-н/Д.: «Феникс», 2014. – 251с .
11. Реан А.А. Психология детства: практикум: тесты, методики для психологов, педагогов, родителей. - С-Пб., 2018. – 521 с.
12. Рождественская Н.В. Креативность: пути развития. СПб.: Питер, 2006.- С.178 - 180.
13. Савенков Л.И. Детская одаренность в познавательной сфере.//Начальная школа. - 2018. - № 5-6. – С.5-9.

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